

TITLE

Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for determination of propofol in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form.

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to develop a simple, precise, accurate, economic and reproducible RP-HPLC method for determination of propofol in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form and validate as per ICH guidelines. In this analysis using C₁₈ column and its dimensions is 250 x 4.6 mm, 5µm with methanol and water for injection as mobile phase in the ratio of 84:16 at flow rate of 0.8 ml/min and detection was carried out at 275 nm by using UV visible detector. The injection volume is 20 µl and retention time was found to be 7min with 18 min as run time. In HPLC method linearity was found in 10-50 µg/ml with correlation coefficient 0.998. The percentage recovery was found to be 99.1 to 100.3 %. The proposed method gave good

separation for propofol and method was validated for accuracy, precision, linearity, limit of detection, limit of quantitation, robustness and ruggedness. The result of study showed that the proposed method RP-HPLC is suitable for routine analysis of itraconazole in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form.

KEYWORD- Propofol, HPLC, Validation, Method development

INTRODUCTION

Propofol is a short acting intravenous aesthetic agent used for the induction of general anesthesia¹. It is 2,6- diisopropylphenol and typically synthesised by isopropylation of phenol over an acid catalyst. It is highly difficult to stabilize bio-oil containing phenolic compounds². Propofol as Diprivans given by injection into veins and maximum effect takes about 2 min to occur and typically lasts five to ten minutes. Common side effect is irregular heart rate, low blood pressure, burning sensation at site of injection and many others may include seizure infection due improper use, addiction³. Propofol is a hypnotic alkylphenol derivative and facilitates inhibitory neurotransmission mediated by gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), this agent is associated with minimal respiratory depression and has a short half-life with duration of action of 2 to 10 minutes⁴. Propofol injectable emulsion is a sterile nonpyrogenic emulsion containing 10 mg/ml of propofol suitable for intravenous administration. It is slightly soluble in water, thus is formulated in a white, oil in

water emulsion⁵. This emulsion is not recommended for induction of anesthesia below age of 3 year or below the age of 2 month because it is not safe⁶. It was discovered in 1977 and approved for use in United States in 1989.

On literature survey it was shown that for the estimation of propofol in blood and plasma or biological fluids by HPLC or other analytical methods were reported^{7,8,9,10} but only single method has been developed and validated for estimation of propofol in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form by RP-HPLC¹¹ and UV-Spectrophotometric¹². Hence an attempt to develop and validate simple, accurate and precise method by R-HPLC.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

HPLC analysis was performed on shimadzu LC 2010CHT, HPLC with supporting software chromeleon or equivalent comprising (shimadzu LC 20AD) pump and C₁₈ kromasil column (agilent zorbax SB) with dimensions is (250 x 4.6 mm, 5µm) separation is based on the isocratic RP chromatography HPLC equipped with suitable UV detector (shimadzu SPD-20 A prominence). A manually operating rheodyne injector with 20 µl sample loop was equipped. Sonicator(KL1.5 Kromo Tech) were also used in this study.

Chemical reagents

Pure form of propofol were procured from baxter pharmaceutical india private limited as gift sample and marketed formulations (DIPRIVIN) emulsion from local pharmacy. Analytical grade methanol was purchased from usha chemotex Mumbai and water for injection from dev life corporation, Mumbai.

Preparation of mobile phase

Prepared a mixture of 84 ml of methanol and 16ml of water for injection, mix well and sonicate for about 5 to 10 min and filtered through 0.45 μm filter paper.

Preparation of working standard solution

10mg of working standard propofol was accurately weighed, transferred to 10 ml volumetric flask and add 2ml of methanol in volumetric flask and shaken well then finally volume make up to 10ml with methanol and it would give concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. From this solution take 1ml transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask, with methanol volume was make up to mark to give concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Like this were prepared solution of different concentration i.e. 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 300 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 400 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively.

Preparation of sample solution

1.0 gm of sample was accurately weighed, transferred into 100ml clean and dry volumetric flask and dilute with methanol then volume made up to 100ml with methanol, mix well the solution for 2 minutes. The solution was filtered through 0.45 μm membrane filter paper (Solution.A). From this solution A, prepared different concentration of sample solution i.e. 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 300 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 400 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively same as standard solution.

Selection of wavelength

For this HPLC analysis suitable wavelength was determined by recording UV spectrum in the range of 200-300nm. For propofol suitable wavelength was selected was 275nm.

Chromatographic conditions

The developed method uses a RPHPLC using C_{18} column (250 x 4.6 mm, 5 μm), mobile phase consists of methanol and water for injection in the ratio of 84:16 at flow rate of 0.8ml/min and volume injected was 20 μl . The mobile phase and sample were degassed by sonication for 15 min and filtered through 0.45 μm membrane filter paper. The detection was carried out at 275nm and UV visible detector was used for this determination. These conditions were ideal for the selected drugs.

Preparation of calibration curves

Different dilutions were prepared separately and 20 μ l of each was injected into HPLC and their chromatogram were recorded after that peak area were recorded for all peaks and curve were plotted.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Method development and optimization

A series of trial were carried out using different mobile phase at different ratio at various flow rate and column temp but final chromatograph was obtained by using these following conditions mention below in the table 1. The chromatograph of standard and sample of propofol (formulations) were shown in the figure 1 and 2. The system suitability test are an integral part of method development and are used to ensure various parameter i.e. tailing factor(T), no. of theoretical plates (N), run time, retention time, resolution, and peaks. The optimized method development resulted in the elution of propofol at 7 min and run time was 18 minutes. The developed method was based upon estimation of the drug by determining the AUC (area under curve) of the chromatogram at selected wavelength. The chromatographic conditions are shown in table no 1.

Table 1- Chromatographic Conditions

Mobile phase	Methanol:water for injection (84:16 v/v)
Detection wavelength	275nm.

Flow rate	0.8 ml/min.
Sample injector	Rheodyne 7725i injector with 20ml loop.
Retention time	7 min
Detector	UV-visible
Run time	18 min
Temperature	Ambient.

fig.1 Chromatogram of standard propofol

fig.2 Chromatogram of formulation of propofol

Method validation parameters

Developed method was validated as per ICH guideline for parameter like system suitability, linearity, accuracy, precision, robustness, ruggedness, LOQ and LOD.

System suitability – System suitability used in method development to ensure adequate performance of chromatograph system. Six replicate injection of standard was given at working concentration. The various parameters come under system suitability like tailing factor, no. of theoretical plates, run time, retention time. Both sample and standard were injected at working

concentration and after that sample peak were identified by comparing with standard peak along with chromatographic conditions. The system suitability criteria were within the acceptance range shown in the table 2

Table 2- System suitability criteria of propofol

Parameter	Acceptance criteria
Theoretical plates	Not less than 1500
Tailing factor	Not more than 2
RSD of all replicate injection	Not more than 2.0 %

Linearity

Linearity of the developed method was determined at different concentration of propofol. The linearity curve was constructed by plotting concentration of propofol versus corresponding peak area as shown in figure 3. The regression coefficient (r^2) was found 0.9987, from the graph it shows that developed method was linear and result are given in the table no 3.

Figure 3 Linearity graph of propofol

Table 3 -Linearity result of propofol

Concentration	Peak area
10	153479
20	225867
30	334567
40	447987
50	558654
60	668965
70	790987
80	890876
90	989876
100	1086789
Slope	10708
intercept	25848
Correlation	0.9987

Accuracy –

The accuracy of propofol was determined by calculating recovery studies of test sample at different concentration (50%,100%,150%) by the standard addition method. Three replicates were injected and mean % recovery of propofol was found within a limit of 98-100% and from result it was found that the developed method was accurate. The % recovery results are shown in table 4.

Table 4- % recovery results for propofol

Level	% recovery	average	SD	%RSD
50%	99.2	99.6	0.43204	0.43378
	100.2			
	99.4			
100%	99.1	95.5	0.54326	0.56926
	99.2			
	100.3			
150%	99.5	99.5	0.24944	0.25069

	99.3			
	99.9			

Precision

Precision was studied to find out intra and inter day variations in the proposed method of propofol at three different concentration levels 60mcg/ml, 80 mcg/ml, 100mcg/ml on the same day and three different day respectively. The % RSD was calculated which should be less than 2%.

Intra day precision

This was done on the same day and the % RSD was calculated, data was present in table 5

Table 5-Intra day precision (Propofol)

S.No	Concentration (mcg/ml)	Injection Volume(ml)	Mean	Standard deviation	%RSD
1	60	20	15872544	90054.79	0.5673
2	80	20	18238219	82971.8	0.4549
3	100	20	20178747	25396.97	0.1258

Mean of three replicate determinations

Inter day precision

This was done on the different day and the % RSD was calculated, data was present in table 6

Table 6 -Inter day precision (Propofol)

S.No	Concentration (mcg/ml)	Injection Volume(ml)	Mean	Standard deviation	%RSD
1	60	20	15250575	67685.62	0.4438
2	80	20	18198958	46570.28	0.2558
3	100	20	20303231	207624.17	1.0226

Mean of three replicate determinations

Ruggedness

The ruggedness study was carried out by analyzing same sample five times by different analyst, on different days using different instruments. The RSD values for the ruggedness study was 0.742331 (Schimadzu) and 1.480034 (Waters) for propofol.

Robustness

This study was done by small deliberate changes in the chromatographic conditions at different levels and retention time was noted for propofol. The factors that selected were small changes in flow rate, detection wavelength range and mobile phase composition. The methods exhibited good robustness because the changes made in chromatographic conditions did not influence the analytical results. Propofol was found stable during procedure.

Mobile phase composition : Methanol : Water for injection

(85 : 15 v/v)

(82 : 18 v/v)

Detection wavelength : 274nm

276nm

Flow rate + 0.9 ml of the target flow rate.

Limit of Detection and Quantification

Limit of detection and quantification of propofol were estimated from the standard deviation (SD) of the response and the slope

(S) of the calibration curve. LOD= 3.3 (SD/S) and LOQ= 10 (SD/S), by applying these formulas LOD and LOQ for Propofol were found to be 1.425mcg/ml and 2.506mcg/ml respectively.

CONCLUSION

High performance liquid chromatography method has been developed for estimation of propofol in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form. This method was validated by various parameter accuracy, precision, linearity, robustness, ruggedness, LOQ and LOD. The method showed good resolution with short analysis time. The developed method was normal, simple, accurate cost effective for determination of propofol. Hence this method could be easily adopted for further analysis of propofol in pharmaceutical dosage form.

Conflicts of Interest: None declared

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